

FACTORS INFLUENCING WORK RESILIENCE OF FILIPINO NURSES IN SELECTED HEALTH FACILITIES IN TARLAC CITY

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ABSTRACT

Nursing is a challenging and stressful profession on its own. The health and well-being of nurses are important as it can greatly affect work performance, and the pressures and demands of the job may possibly lead to various physical and mental health problems. Building resilience is recognized as an important factor to help nurses remain in the profession. This study was conducted to determine the level of work resilience, and the factors associated with it. An analytical cross-sectional design was utilized in the study. Data were analyzed using descriptive statistics and Spearman's correlation. The findings revealed moderate resiliency in how nurses manage their stress at work, while a partially high resiliency was seen in how nurses maintain their physical fitness, healthy diet, and work composure. The overall work resilience of nurses was found to be at high levels among Filipino nurses. It is concluded that overall work resilience is influenced by financial situation and health condition. Further study is recommended to explore other mediating factors in work resilience.

Keywords: *Filipino Nurses, Work Resilience*

INTRODUCTION

The world population needed nurses who frequently served as the first and sometimes the only health professionals that provided a quality health assessment, care, and treatment which is very important not only during the critical stage of every patient but until the recovery and rehabilitation phase of the treatment process (WHO, 2022).

Philippines remained to be at lower-middle economic status (Cordero, 2024), and there are more private hospitals than public hospitals in the country (Silva et al., 2020). Despite being one of the main producers of nurses around the world, the country still faces challenges with the shortage of capable nurses within its healthcare system, wherein stress and burnout are becoming a recurring problem for Filipino nurses who remained working in the country (Alibudbud, 2023). Private health facilities mostly suffer from nurse shortages, with financial incentives alone do not guarantee the nurses to stay working in hospitals (Biluan et. al., 2023).

Many factors, like salary insufficiencies as compared to high cost of living, understaffing that leads to increased workload, and insecurities in the workplace, could all result in burnout and issues with mental health among nurses (Corpuz, 2023). As cited by Lacsamana (2021), the result of the survey conducted by the International Congress of Nurses (2021) showed that over 70% of nurses from the national nurses' associations worldwide claimed that predicting factors outside or inside the nurses' workplace, such as people's negativity and lack of support from the organization, had resulted in extreme cases of psychological distress and mental health pressure.

To thrive professionally and handle pressures at work, nurses must possess a high degree of resilience (Walpita & Arambepola, 2019). Studies have shown that resilience helps nurses reduce the effects of stress and burnout (Yu et al. 2019). Also, a resilient nurse with better financial security and are physically and mentally healthy can cope effectively with stress, leading to improved focus, appropriate decision-making, and most importantly, a higher level of quality care for patients (Jamebozorgi et al., 2022 and Hughes et al., 2024).

This study explored the level of work resilience and which among the sociodemographic factors had influenced the resilience at work of Filipino nurses. It aimed at providing assessment that will prove beneficial in the development of the appropriate programs intended for staff's wellbeing. Although there are already some studies that have explored resilience in nurses, these studies were done in different countries and settings and yield varying results that cannot be assumed to be applicable to Filipino nurses. Additionally, there is a dearth of literature published on work resilience among Filipino registered nurses.

Research Questions

This study aimed to determine the factors influencing the work resilience of Filipino registered nurses.

Specifically, it seeks to answer the following questions:

1. What is the sociodemographic profile of the respondents in terms of:
 - 1.1 Age
 - 1.2 Gender
 - 1.3 Civil Status
 - 1.4 Highest Educational Attainment
 - 1.5 Years of Experience in the Profession

- 1.6 Length of Service in the Current Institution
 - 1.7 Hours of Work
 - 1.8 Occupied Position/Rank at Work
 - 1.9 Financial Situation
 - 1.10 Health Condition
 2. How is the level of work resilience of the respondent be described in terms of:
 - 2.1 Living authentically,
 - 2.2 Finding one's calling,
 - 2.3 Maintaining perspective,
 - 2.4 Managing stress,
 - 2.5 Staying healthy,
 - 2.6 Building social connection.
 3. Which among the sociodemographic profiles has a relationship with work resilience in terms of:
 - 3.1 Living authentically,
 - 3.2 Finding one's calling,
 - 3.3 Maintaining perspective,
 - 3.4 Managing stress,
 - 3.5 Staying healthy,
 - 3.6 Building social connection.
 4. Is there a significant relationship between the sociodemographic profile and the overall level of work resilience?
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METHODOLOGY

This study used the analytical cross-sectional design to investigate the level of work resilience of registered Filipino nurses working in selected secondary and tertiary hospitals in Tarlac City and was conducted within the period of SY 2023-2024. A non-probability sampling technique called purposive sampling was used to select the Filipino registered nurses who were currently employed in a health facility within the province of Tarlac with at least 3 years of working experience in the profession. The primary tool used in this study is a standardized and adopted questionnaire, which is the Resilience at Work (RAW) scale. This was developed by Winwood et al. (2013) and revised by Malik & Garg (2018), containing 17 items rated on a 7-point Likert scale to measure one's management of the pressures of work with a reliability score of $\alpha = 0.81$.

The sociodemographic profile of the Filipino registered nurses was described using frequency counts and percentages. While the levels of work resilience in terms of the six components were described based on the following ranges and were presented as follows:

<u>Range</u>	<u>Verbal Interpretations</u>
6.16 to 7.00	Very High Resilience
5.30 to 6.15	High Resilience
4.44 to 5.29	Partially High Resilience
3.58 to 4.43	Moderate Resilience
2.72 to 3.57	Partially Low Resilience
1.86 to 2.71	Low Resilience
1.00 to 1.85	Very Low Resilience

The correlations between the socio-demographic profile of the respondents and six Resilience at Work (RAW) components and the relationship between the socio-demographic profile and the overall RAW were analysed using Spearman's correlation.

RESULTS

Descriptive Analysis

Table 1. Sociodemographic Profile of the Respondents

	<i>Category</i>	<i>Frequency</i>	<i>Percentage</i>
Age	25 to 30	37	35.92%
	31 to 36	42	40.78%
	37 to 42	17	16.50%
	43 to 48	4	3.88%
	49 to 54	3	2.91%
	<i>Total</i>	<i>103</i>	<i>100%</i>
Gender	Man	27	26.21%
	Woman	72	69.90%
	Other	4	3.88%
	<i>Total</i>	<i>103</i>	<i>100%</i>
Civil Status	Single	59	57.28%
	Married	42	40.78%
	Separated	1	0.97%
	Widowed	1	0.97%
	<i>Total</i>	<i>103</i>	<i>100%</i>
Highest Educational Attainment	Bachelor of Nursing	84	81.55%
	Master of Nursing	19	18.45%
	<i>Total</i>	<i>103</i>	<i>100%</i>
Years of Experience in the Profession	3 to 8	58	56.31%
	9 to 14	30	29.13%
	15 to 20	12	11.65%
	21 to 26	0	0.00%
	27 to 32	3	2.91%

	<i>Total</i>	103	100%
Length of Service in the Current Institution	1 to 5	67	65.05%
	6 to 10	30	29.13%
	11 to 15	5	4.85%
	16 to 20	0	0.00%
	21 to 25	1	0.97%
	<i>Total</i>	103	100%
Hours of work per day	8 hours	33	33.04%
	12 hours	70	67.96%
	<i>Total</i>	103	100%
Occupied Position/Rank at Work	Staff Nurse	69	66.99%
	Head Nurse	18	17.48%
	Chief Nurse	3	2.91%
	Nurse Supervisor	9	8.74%
	Other	4	3.88%
	<i>Total</i>	103	100%
Financial Situation	Good	59	57.28%
	Bad	2	1.94%
	Neither good nor bad	42	40.78%
	<i>Total</i>	103	100%
Health Condition	Very Good	21	20.39%
	Good	63	61.17%
	Neither good nor bad	11	10.68%
	Bad	8	7.77%
	<i>Total</i>	103	100%

Table 2. Level of Resilience at Work (RAW)

<i>Components</i>	<i>Mean</i>	<i>Verbal Description</i>
Living Authentically	5.98	High Resilience
Finding One's Calling	5.78	High Resilience
Maintaining Perspective	5.01	Partially High Resilience
Managing Stress	5.55	High Resilience
Building Social Connections	6.09	High Resilience
Staying Healthy	5.11	Partially High Resilience
Overall Resilience at Work	5.58	High Resilience

Correlational Statistics

Table 3. Relationship of Resilience at Work (RAW) to Sociodemographic Profile

<i>Component of RAW</i>	<i>Sociodemographic profile</i>	<i>r value</i>	<i>p value</i>	<i>Decision</i>	<i>Remarks</i>
Living authentically	Age	0.239*	0.015	Reject Ho	Significant
	Years of Experience in the Profession	0.293*	0.003	Reject Ho	Significant
	Financial Situation	0.369*	0.000	Reject Ho	Significant
Finding one's calling	Civil status	-0.465*	0.000	Reject Ho	Significant
	Hours of work per day	-0.240*	0.015	Reject Ho	Significant
Maintaining perspective	Age	-0.277*	0.005	Reject Ho	Significant
	Gender	0.236*	0.017	Reject Ho	Significant
	Civil status	0.234*	0.018	Reject Ho	Significant
	Financial Situation	0.217*	0.028	Reject Ho	Significant
Managing stress	Length of Service in the Current Institution	-0.259*	0.008	Reject Ho	Significant
	Financial Situation	0.391*	0.000	Reject Ho	Significant
	Health Condition	-0.219*	0.026	Reject Ho	Significant
Staying healthy	Age	0.299*	0.002	Reject Ho	Significant
	Years of Experience in the Profession	0.233*	0.018	Reject Ho	Significant
	Financial Situation	0.274*	0.005	Reject Ho	Significant
	Health Condition	-0.583*	0.000	Reject Ho	Significant
Building social connection	Highest Educational Attainment	-0.245*	0.013	Reject Ho	Significant
	Years of Experience in the Profession	-0.207*	0.036	Reject Ho	Significant
	Financial Situation	0.277*	0.005	Reject Ho	Significant
Overall RAW	Financial Situation	0.400*	0.000	Reject Ho	Significant
	Health Condition	-0.323*	0.001	Reject Ho	Significant

DISCUSSION

Sociodemographic Profile of the Respondents

Nurses who participated in the study mostly belonged to the age group ranging from 31 to 36 and 69.90% of these nurses were women. Furthermore, in terms of civil status, most of them were single with a bachelor's degree and they still had not yet taken or finished

their master's degree program. In terms of the years of experience in the profession, a big slab of the sample had three to eight years of experience yet most of them had one to five years of length of service in their current institution. Also, it was notable that there was one respondent who has spent 25 years in one selected health facility in Tarlac city. Moreover, 67.96% of the Filipino registered nurses worked 12 hours per day and most of these respondents were staff nurses. Lastly, in terms of financial situation and health condition, most of the registered nurses perceived their situation/condition were under good state.

Level of Resilience at Work (RAW)

Resilience in nurses is their ability to bounce back from challenges, adapt to stressful situations, and maintain their well-being. The levels of resilience can be categorized as low, moderate, or high. Nurses with low resilience often struggle to cope with workplace stressors, while nurses with moderate resilience possess some coping skills but may still experience challenges. And nurses with high resilience demonstrate exceptional ability to cope with adversity (Walpita & Arambepola, 2019).

Results of this study show a high level of overall resiliency of Filipino nurses and in terms of their authentic life, sense of purpose in life, stress management, and how they connect or interact with others inside or outside their workplace. This high level of resiliency from the respondents exhibits a sample of strong emotional regulation wherein they can manage their emotions effectively in challenging situations. Wherein a person who lives authentically has a good well-being and is most likely to engage and adapt well to their working environment (Sutton, 2020). While nurses with good self-esteem, self-efficacy, and a sense of connectedness to work or profession can greatly contribute to increasing the number of nurse retentions in hospitals (Reinhardt et al., 2020). Employees who can effectively manage stress and cultivate strong family relationships showcase successful work-life balance (Irawanto et al., 2021). And research finding by Sulimani-Aidan & Tayri-Schwartz (2021) state that social support could assist in achieving a sense of belonging, provide emotional comfort, and neutralize stress. Social connections also enhance nurses' sense of belonging, purpose, and self-worth, and the role of social support is directly related to promoting emotional regulation, problem-solving, and coping skills.

Another result of this study shows a partially high resiliency in terms of nurses' capabilities to manage setbacks, focus on solutions, properly deal with negativity in the workplace, and how they maintained their physical health. From these components, it was revealed that respondents demonstrated limited but relevant ability to cope and recover from challenges they faced in their everyday working shifts. A similar study was also conducted by Sawatzky (2022), which concluded that the capacity to maintain composure and focus can be an asset in demanding work environments. And individuals who are not easily fazed often demonstrate greater efficiency, problem-solving abilities, and decision-making skills under pressure. While Belcher et al. and Arida & Teixeira-Machado (2021) stated that aerobic fitness is a key factor in achieving resilience. Eating a healthy diet in collaboration with physical activity and exercise can be powerful tools to build resilience which strengthen brain functions related to self-control, potentially acting as a neutralizer against mental health problem.

Relationship of Resilience at Work (RAW) to Sociodemographic Profile

This study found out that among the sociodemographic factors of the respondents, only the financial situation and health conditions are correlated to the overall resilience at work of the respondents. The unyielding dedication and commitment among Filipino nurses can be affected by having low salaries. An income that could support their everyday needs and living could become an additional motivation for them to remain resilient and to render quality care to their patients. This finding is supported by the study of Jamebozorgi et al. (2022), stating that financially secured nurses may experience less stress related to financial burdens, potentially leading to increased productivity and efficiency.

On the other hand, a negative relationship was found between the overall RAW and health condition of nurses. Although the statistical findings of the study revealed a weak relationship, this still means that the resiliency of nurses at work increases even though their health deviates from a normal condition. Filipino nurses possessed abilities to still smile during difficult times, can remain calm, and still do their work despite feeling of uneasiness because of certain alterations in their health conditions. Nurses learned how to tolerate such personal problems just to do their job properly. But this contradicts the study of Hughes et al. (2024), which reveals that resilient nurses who were physically and mentally healthy may provide better focus, improved decision-making, and higher quality care for patients. Also, according to the same study, healthy nurses with a strong capacity to manage stress were less prone to errors due to fatigue or emotional strain, leading to a safer environment for patients.

Data analysed in this study showed a significant positive relationship from Living Authentically and Staying Healthy to the respondent's age, financial situation, and years of experience in the profession. Nurses' work resilience in terms of the mentioned two components becomes higher as they get older, earn more income, and gain more experience in their chosen career. Nurses face different challenges over time, and as they accumulate life experiences, they may also develop a clearer sense of their values, priorities, and aspirations. The study of Rumjaun & Narod (2020) that holds on the Social Learning Theory, which stated that with increasing age and professional experience, individuals accumulate a wealth of knowledge and skills, which can contribute to a stronger sense of self and purpose.

Also, with regards to the negative correlation between Finding One's Calling and the respondent's civil status as well as the number of hours they work per day. Nurses are more likely to hold on to their values and beliefs and maintain their sense of belonging and purpose in life when they are still not married and work in the hospital for fewer hours a day as compared with the other shift schedules. Their sense of purpose and calling could sometimes be affected by their priorities in life, especially when they already have their own families or have experienced a higher workload from a longer span of duty hours in the hospital. nurses' efforts to maintain patient rights according to their values and beliefs, like when facing ethical dilemmas, could elevate their personal satisfaction from helping their patients, but were challenged by occupational burnout (Tehranineshat et al., 2020),

This study also unveiled that managing stress is negatively correlated with the respondent's length of service in the current health institution. This implies that nurses are more likely to be able to deal with their everyday stressors, preserve a work-life balance, and lend time for relaxation when they are still under probationary or adjustment periods at work for the earlier years of work under their present employer. Nurses, despite how long they are already working in the same hospital, may still develop stress and decrease resiliency in the absence of follow-up measures (Andersen et al., 2021).

The researcher also found out that as the respondents gained more experience as professional nurses and as they sought to learn more from continuing education in graduate programs, they were also finding difficulty in establishing their personal support system inside or outside the health facility. Many mediating factors needed to answer these findings that were not included in this study, such as the decrease in the hours they spent socializing with others due to diversion of those times to their graduate studies and also due to increased workload during and after work shifts because of a higher position they received from the hospital administration when they finished their graduate degree and acquired long years of working experience. All of this might become a hindrance to preserving their support system, which is needed to maintain or increase the level of their work resilience. The same research findings by Sulimani-Aidan & Tayri-Schwartz (2021) state that social support provides emotional comfort and practical assistance, which also acts as a coping tool against stress.

Conclusions

Based on the findings of this study, it is concluded that the Filipino nurses, despite some certain factors that could influence their wellbeing, are found to have a high level of resilience at work. Financial and health conditions are the factors that have significant influence on the overall work resilience of Filipino nurses.

Recommendations

To maintain the high level of nurses' resilience at work and good health, hospital management and leaders may review programs that address and focus on workplace and staff wellbeing, flexible work schedules, and additional policies that promote employee assistance. Future research may consider the use of other factors and/or mediating variables and methodology to further explore the work resilience of nurses.

Compliance with Ethical Standards

In the conduct of this study, ethical considerations were strictly observed by the researcher. Permission was secured from concerned authorities in their health institution or facility, and informed consent was obtained from the study participants that provided detailed information of the purpose of the study. Voluntary participation was maintained, wherein they could withdraw anytime, while anonymity was observed by using code numbers for identification. All information shared was treated with the utmost confidentiality by not sharing it with anyone and using passwords for databases. After the

completion of the study, all data was deleted from the system or source. No conflict of interest exists in the conduct of the study, plagiarism was strictly avoided, there was no bias in the interpretation of the findings and that the results were used purely for research.

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